

HOW TO IMPROVE ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract: This article deals with some kind of advice improving speaking skills with new techniques and various methods for learn to speak English. In this piece of writing it was analyzed some effective ways to improve speaking levels. It provides some thought about imitating, reading or listening, conversation, and keep talking methods their valuable process which is helpful tool in developing speaking skills.

Keywords: native speaker, speaking, implicit learning, some step to improve speaking, keep talking.

Nowadays, the number of English language learners is increasing day by day. Many people have difficulty in speaking English. Now I will tell you some ways to speak English fast and fluently.

1. Listen

The first step in improving your speaking skills is actually working on your listening. Listening to English has several benefits it allows you to pick up new words, phrases and ways to respond in conversations. Then it helps to us for understanding pronunciation, how some words are joined together the rhythm, and the sounds of language. Everyday listening English podcast BBS or listen to audiobooks and other types of podcast are a popular way to listen to English and develop your listening and speaking skills.

2. Read

Reading is a very important skill when learning language. Whether you prefer a novel, books or an article, reading a few minutes every day will help you acquire new vocabulary when learning English, reading for a few minutes is greatly is beneficial. Short articles, story or notes in English are greatly for this.

3. Imitate

Now that you have listened to lots of English conversations it's time for some imitation. Yes, that's right! Imitating or copying someone is a wonderful to improve your speaking skill. Another benefit of imitation is that it will help you become more accurate in English without having to learn grammar rules. With lots of practice you

will begin to remember chunks of words and phrases. Repeat and record: after playing the audio, repeat saying the words and conversations exactly as you heard. Record yourself while repeating the words help to us to listen to our self and self-correct. Compare: listen to the audio again and compare it with your recording.

4. Learn new words every day

Choose a word you would like to work on and use practice it in different sentences. Use the word until you have learnt it and keep using it regularly.

5. Watch films

Watch movies in English and pay attention to new vocabulary and pronunciation, imitate the actors and have fun with it.

6. Make friends and do interesting activities.

Make friends with English speakers or other learning to speak English and compare notes. Talk about things that you have learnt and exchange ideas. Another way is doing an activity that you enjoy it in English.

7. Have a debate

Debate all the topics that interest you with friends in English. Try to use as much vocabulary as you can to get your point across and listen to the other arguments carefully so you can argue against them effectively.

8. Use a dictionary

Nowadays online dictionary users is a lot .Online dictionaries often have audio examples so you can check your pronunciation and there are lots of great dictionary apps that you can take everywhere with you on your phone. There is a best way for improving speaking English language.

With enough motivation and effort, you can see certain improvements in your speaking skills in as little as two weeks. However, how much progress you make will depend on several factors, such as your current level of language, how often you practice, and what types of activities you do to practice.

Talking about the time the development of speaking skills takes, it is important to keep in mind that everyone learns at a different pace. While some people may be able to become conversationally fluent in around a year, others may need a few years. The most important thing is to remain patient and consistent with your effort. Do not get discouraged if you don't see the results you want immediately. With time and practice, you will get there!

If you want to know how to speak better English and have more structure and guidance, consider signing up for a course. There are many different types of courses available, from online programs to in-person classes.

Taking a course can be especially helpful if you are struggling with a particular aspect of the language, especially speaking or pronunciation. It can also be a great way to meet other people who are learning English and make friends that can help support your efforts.

Finally, don't forget to have fun. It's easier to learn something new and commit to learning when you're having fun. Practice English by singing along to popular songs. Practice tongue twisters with your friends.

Try all these tips today and start your language learning journey right away!

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